

RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING(RTM): EXPERIMENTS WITH VACUUM ASSISTED METHODS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a comparison of the effect of Vacuum Assist Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM) to basic Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) on the quality, primarily micro-void content, of fabricated composite panels. It is generally accepted that VARTM should provide composites with lower void content but in practice such has not often been the case. This work addresses some of the reasons for this discrepancy. All experiments utilized 8-harness satin weave graphite fabric compressed to as much as 54 volume percent fiber and Dow Chemical's Tactix 123 epoxy matrix. The research reported is primarily experimental. The experimental results of the fill sequence is recorded visually by a video camera through a transparent mold face and the molded composite panels are analyzed for void content with an Ultrasonic C-scan. The results quantify the importance of the VARTM process with a vacuum tight mold for minimizing micro-voids.

Keywords: RTM, resin transfer molding, graphite-epoxy composite, vacuum assisted resin transfer molding, micro-voids, c-scan, void content

INTRODUCTION

Advanced polymeric based composites for use in the aerospace industry are most often fabricated in an autoclave. The autoclave process has proven to be a reliable method for fabrication because it yields a quality composite with low void content, high fiber volume and uniform cure. The down-side of the autoclave process is:

- expensive capital equipment (autoclave)
- relatively costly raw materials (expensive prepreg)
- long processing times (8 hours for autoclave turnaround)
- high energy consumption (heating and cooling massive tooling and equipment)
- labor intensive (layup and bagging)

The down-side factors listed above are major cost factors that make advanced composites consolidated in an autoclave very expensive to produce and beyond the budget for many potential applications. Another less costly fabrication process, Resin Transfer Molding(RTM), has been an industrially viable manufacturing process for commercial grade composites for many years. The RTM process is most often described as injecting a liquid catalyzed thermosetting resin matrix into a closed mold containing a positioned reinforcement fiber preform. For typical commercial applications, the matrix would be polyester resin and the reinforcement fibers would be glass. This process has been particularly advantageous for fabricating production quantities of large complex composite parts. Many variations of this process are in use at this time which are custom designed to address particular fabrication problems. However, this process has not been widely used to fabricate advanced aerospace grade composites because typically the void content is considered to be too high and the fiber volume content too low.

Research on advanced composites is being conducted at N.C. State University and N.C. A & T State

University, and other places based on complex 3-D textile preforms. Some of the mechanical properties obtained on advanced composites fabricated utilizing these preforms has caught the imagination of designers, particularly where through-the-thickness strength is required. The residual strength after impact has been found to be impressive (1). Unfortunately it is not practical to put prepreg materials through the textile fabricating equipment required to produce the 3-D textile preforms. Prepreg with tack tends to stick to the various mechanisms and prepreg without tack tends to be brittle and the matrix flakes-off as it passes through the equipment mechanisms. Without prepreg as a raw material, the autoclave process is not attractive and hence an alternate fabrication process like the RTM becomes the process of choice.

The basic approach in this paper was directed toward exploring techniques for lowering the void content and raising fiber volume of RTM fabricated composites to a level competitive to autoclave processed composites. Another factor that makes the use of the RTM process practical is the recent introduction of matrix resins that are equal in mechanical properties to those used in prepreps but are capable of being processed by the RTM process.

Much of the development work reported in the literature on RTM has been directed toward mold filling which, of course, is of great concern (2). An RTM composite molding in which the preform is not completely filled with matrix, leaving dry fibers, is often a cause for scrap or at least an expensive rework operation. Numerous investigators have mathematically modeled mold filling procedure at a macroscopic scale utilizing modifications of Darcy's law with the ultimate objective of obtaining a complete fill without trapping pockets of air. These models have been found to be useful for optimizing the location of the injection port and the vent holes (3).

This paper will deal with micro-voids at high fiber volumes which is a different aspect of mold filling than much of the research performed in the past. This work is directed toward void content and fiber volumes similar to those obtainable by the autoclave process. The effect of this type of void on the mechanical properties of graphite/epoxy composites has been established by Ghiorse (4). In this paper micro-voids are defined as those small voids contained within the matrix, and dry fibers are not involved.

One way to minimize void content in a composite is by the application of a vacuum both to the liquid matrix before it is introduced into the mold and the evacuation the mold before and during the introduction of the liquid matrix into the mold. The experimental procedure adapted for the study was designed to compare the void content of composites which were fabricated by mold filling with and without the application of vacuum to the mold before and during the filling process. In either case the matrix was degassed by evacuation to minimize the voids being introduced with the matrix.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

RTM Mold Design And Preparation

A composite panel size of 254 X 280 X 2.5 mm was selected for this study. A sketch of the cross section of the mold containing the preform is shown in Figure 1. The mold cavity was fabricated out of steel and a cover plate was machined out of clear acrylic sheet to provide a cavity depth of 2.5 mm.

Figure 1. Cross-section of RTM mold containing the preform

The liquid matrix was introduced into the mold at one end and three vent holes were provided at the opposite end to allow air to escape or for vacuum to be applied. Silicone sealer (bathtub caulk) was applied at the mold parting line to prevent the matrix from leaking and to prevent a vacuum leak for those experiments where vacuum was applied to the mold. The silicone sealer was also applied along the edges of the graphite fiber preform as well to eliminate the opportunity for liquid matrix to bypass the preform. Earlier experiments provided proof that it was necessary to seal the edges. A space was allowed at the edge of the preform at the gate end of the mold to allow for a manifold effect which allowed the liquid matrix to fill along that entire edge of the preform before entering the preform. The edge opposite the fill gate contained three vent or overflow holes. The preform was sealed along this edge also except for the vent holes themselves. This prevented the liquid matrix from freely flowing along the preform vent edge and provide an opportunity to trap an air pocket. Figure 3 illustrates the regular RTM (RRTM) setup and Figure 4 the vacuum assist RTM (VARTM) process setup.

Fiber Selection

Another factor in the experiment was to use a complex graphite fiber preform with high fiber volume that could be easily reproduced in the laboratory. The 3-D textile preforms which had been the subject of other studies in our laboratory were ruled out because they were expensive to prepare and somewhat variable because the equipment was only semiautomatic and often contained an element of operator variability. Woven 8-harness satin weave graphite cloth was selected for this study because it was uniform, could be readily cut to size and reliably stacked to obtain controlled fiber volume.

A preform with a high degree of uniformity is relatively easy to fill by the RTM process. It was decided to increase the degree of difficulty by varying the fiber volume within the preform. The fiber volume was varied by adding "patches" of woven fabric at various locations in the preform to provide an obstacle course for the matrix flow.

The preform was prepared by cutting six 280 x 254 mm layers, one layer of circular disc donut shape (external diameter 116 mm and internal diameter 37 mm), two layers of circular shape 50 mm diameter each and one layer of circular shape 41 mm diameter from the 8-harness satin weave graphite fabric. Two pieces of closed cell urethane foam 280 x 12.5 x 1.6 mm for use to seal the edges of mold were also prepared.

Figure 2. Ply stacking sequence to induce controlled fiber volume change by using fabric patches

Mold Preparation

The mold was cleaned and a mold release was applied to the entire mold surface. The mold release used was Trewax. This is a common floor wax compound that contains carnuba wax. It was applied with a cloth and later hand buffed to polish and remove the excess wax. Using the sequence shown in Figure 2, the preform was placed in the cavity of the mold. The closed cell urethane foam was placed at each edge of the preform and silicone sealer applied to seal the mold as shown in Figure 1. The mold was secured tight with bolts, and set-up vertically ready for resin injection as shown in Figure 3.

Matrix Preparation

The matrix system was Dow Chemical's Tactix 123 resin, and catalyst was Milliken Chemical's Millamine 5260. The ratio of this system was 100 parts by weight of resin and 17 parts by weight of catalyst and in addition one percent white color paste (TiO_2) was added. The small amount of white color paste was added to the liquid matrix to enhance its visibility through the acrylic mold cover as the matrix fill proceeds. After proportioning and mixing, the liquid matrix was degassed in a vacuum chamber for 5 minutes at 700 millitorr to eliminate the possibility of introducing micro-voids within the matrix.

RTM Mold Filling

The matrix was pumped into the mold with the aid of a peristaltic pump. Since this provides a method of containing the liquid matrix in a rubber hose, cleanup operations are minimized. The peristaltic pump provides for constant flow with the pressure increasing as more resistance to flow is encountered. To minimize the variables in the experimental process, all of the fills were conducted at room temperature. For actual part fabrication, no doubt, the matrix and mold would be at elevated temperature to take advantage of lower viscosity, faster fill times and a faster cure. The fill experiments were recorded with a Camcorder for future comparison.

Three different versions of RTM mold filling process were used; regular RTM (RRTM), vacuum assist RTM (VARTM) and the controlled leak vacuum assist RTM (CLVRTM). The set-up for each of the methods is as shown in Figures 3 through 5. In the RRTM method the prepared matrix resin was poured into the resin reservoir and pumped into the mold cavity, a dial gauge was used to measure increase in diameter of the Norprene tubing in order to determine resin injection pressure. When the mold was filled, resin began exiting the vent ports and when this exiting resin was free of air bubbles, the pump was shut off, and the vents and injection Norprene tube were clamped. In the case of the VARTM method, vacuum was applied at the vent tubes prior to pumping and is terminated before the pumps are stopped. Vacuum gages were employed at the top and bottom of the mold to measure the vacuum pressure. The bottom gage verified the vacuum level in the mold before the filling began. The CLVRTM method, Figure 5, is similar to the VARTM, except that a controlled air leak was introduced into the mold after the resin front has advanced past the position of each of the four air leak tubes. The experiment was repeated for each of the above methods using three different pump settings (Table 2, Flow Rate) in order to determine the effect of flow rate on the resulting void content.

Curing Process

The matrix selected for this study allowed for the initial cure (80°C for 1 hour) to be conducted with the acrylic cover in place. The composite panel was then removed from the mold and post cured in an oven at 177°C for 2 hours.

Figure 3. Setup for regular resin transfer molding (RRTM)

Figure 4. Setup for vacuum assist resin transfer molding (VARTM)

Figure 5. Vacuum assist resin transfer molding with controlled leak (CLVRTM)

ANALYSIS OF RTM COMPOSITE PANELS

Fiber Volume

The fiber volume fraction was determined by using the acid digestion method. Table 1 gives the results for the various fabric plies in the molded panels.

Composite Density

The composite panel density was determined by the "water displacement" method

Void Content Determination

The micro-void content was determined with a Ultrasonic C-scan device. C-scan measurements have become common for determining the location and extent of delamination. The use of C-scan for the determination of micro-void content has not been established to our knowledge. To verify the usefulness of the C-scan for determining micro-void content, a sample with known micro-void content must be fabricated. This task has not been completed. The void content was determined using a Sonotek's Ultrasonic C-scan which utilizes a pulse-echo method. The C-scan consists of 1) a three axis (X,Y & Z) stepper motor controlled scanning bridge, 2) a Sonotek MC 33 stepper motor controller (indexer card plus driver pack), 3) a Sonotek STR*8100 100 Megahertz analog to digital converter board, and 4) an IBM compatible computer and an ultrasonic Pulser/Receiver and transducer. Figure 6 shows the experimental set-up for the scanning of the molded composite panels.

Scanning was carried out using the following transducer and settings:

• Transducer type	15 MHz
• Attenuation	22 dB
• Energy setting	3
• Gain	normal
• Damping	6
• Hp filter	1.0

A key advantage of this Sonotek's System is that it was designed to offer its users a completely digital high resolution scanning and data acquisition package for generating color coded amplitude and time-of-flight (TOF) images. Collected data stored in the computer, is accessed using Sonotek's C-View image enhancement program, where the defect sizing window is used to determine the dimensions of the defects (percentage of void content) from the C-Scan plot.

Both sides of the panel were inspected in order to detect all defects. Results are representative of the total void content (both sides) for each panel which is tabulated in Table 2. The results reported are comparative only and further work is required to determine the actual micro-void content by C-Scan. Work on this is continuing.

Figure 6. Setup of ultrasonic C-SCAN for composite Panel

RESULTS

The fiber volume fraction of the panel containing various layers was determined using the acid digestion method. The results were found to be within reasonable limit, including the specific gravity determinations as shown in Table 1. The data indicates the standard panel utilized in this study includes fiber volumes range from 30 to 54%. The void content obtained were seen to be influenced by the flow rate of resin injection for all types of the RTM methods. As the flow rate increased, the void content also increased as indicated in Table 2. The experimental results in Table 2 also indicate that the use of vacuum assistance aids the infiltration process in a well sealed mold (VARTM). This was seen to result in a very low micro-void content, 0.15% maximum, while in a poorly sealed mold (CLVRTM), resulted in a very high void content, 4.53% maximum.

No. of Plies	Specific Gravity	Fiber Volume(%)
5	1.389	30.1
6	1.437	39.7
7	1.496	48.0
8	1.520	53.8

Table 1. Fiber volume at various ply levels

Panel No.	Flow Rate g/min.	Processing Method *	Void Content %
1	20	RRTM	0.38
2	20	VARTM	0.12
3	28	RRTM	0.59
4	28	VARTM	0.11
5	35	RRTM	1.67
6	35	VARTM	0.15
7	20	CLVRTM	4.53

* RRTM = Regular RTM
 VARTM = Vacuum assisted RTM
 CLVRTM = Controlled Leak Vacuum RTM

Table 2. Void content by RTM method and flow rate

DISCUSSION

Contrary to the views that have been expressed in past, research findings that the vacuum assist RTM has not become widely accepted because of reportedly large porosities, this paper helps to reaffirm that the use of vacuum assist (VARTM) to aid the resin infiltration process is very effective in situations

where the mold is properly sealed, resulting with a low percentage of void content. This was not the case with an improperly sealed mold (CLVRTM) which resulted in a very high void content. These results are clearly demonstrated in Table 2.

The use of graphite fabric as opposed to glass increased the degree of difficulty of the resin impregnation process. Graphite unlike glass is not easily wetted out by the resin. Selection of 2-D weave in preference to 3-D textile preforms provided uniformity and the possibility of obtaining a variable stacking sequence to obtain controlled fiber volume.

The monitoring of the resin flow with a video camera resulted in an improved understanding of void formation mechanism. As the flow front encounters the circular donut patches (high fiber volume areas) it flows around it entrapping a pocket of air. In the RRTM and CLVRTM processes, the voids resulting from the air entrapment remained. While in the VARTM, imposed vacuum on a well sealed mold led to absence of an opposing pressure in the entrapped void and as the process continued void eventually collapsed, which explains the reason for the lowest void content obtained (Table 2) by this method.

The RTM steel mold ensures durability and the acrylic plastic upper mold surface enabled video recording of the advancing resin front. The inlet port allows for lower resin injection pressure and the three vent ports allow air being displaced by incoming resin and the exiting resin to escape.

The Tactix 123 resin and catalyst (Millamine 5260) resin systems selected adhered well to the graphite fabric. The chemical reaction between the resin and the curing agent does not release any volatiles or water.

CONCLUSIONS

A review of the data provides sufficient information to draw the following conclusions:

- With regular resin transfer molding (RRTM) process, an increase in fill rate results in an increase in micro-void content.
- With the vacuum assist resin transfer molding (VARTM) process, the fill rate could be increased without causing the micro-void content to increase.
- If the mold used in the vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) is not properly sealed, the micro-void content increases dramatically.

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